

Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming-Based Unit Commitment of Conventional Thermal Generators Using Hybrid Evolutionary Algorithms

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Abstract

Unit Commitment (UC) discusses the optimized generation resources (to turn on economical generators and turn off expensive generators), which are subjected to satisfy all the operational constraints. The operational constraints such as load balancing, security maximization, minimum up and down time, spinning reserve, and ramp up and down constraints are difficult to satisfy. Although, UC is a cost minimization problem that is realized by committing less expensive units while satisfying the corresponding constraints, and dispatching the committed units economically. The UC problem is an np-hard Mixed Integer Nonlinear Problem (MINLP). Therefore, in this paper, hybrid EA based on a Genetic Algorithm (GA) has been applied to find the optimal solution to the UC problem. Moreover, during the search process, it is very difficult to discard infeasible solutions in EAs. Hence, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) is integrated with the feasibility rule constraint handling technique to emphasize feasible solutions. IEEE RTS Eleven Thermal Generator Standard Test system is used to validate the performance of proposed methods. For the validation and the superiority of the proposed algorithm, simulation results are compared with the classical Lagrangian Relaxation (LR) methods. Results show that the proposed method can find the global optimal solution to the UC problem which is subjected to satisfy all the operational constraints.

Index Terms: Constraint Handling Techniques, Economic Dispatch, Evolutionary Algorithms, Mixed Integer, Unit Commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Unit Commitment (UC) is a complex np-hard, non-convex, mixed-integer nonlinear problem where the cost of generators is minimized to obtain the best schedule of units [1]. Optimizing electricity generation provides numerous benefits to market participants and end users [2]. As a result of the problem's magnitude and computational constraints, nevertheless, it is not a simple task. Due to this, numerous works in the literature suggest various methods for resolving this issue in the best possible way, making them a crucial area for operational research advancements. To correctly operate the generators and reduce costs, the UC must decide which generators to turn on and which to turn off based on demand. These generators must also be economically dispatched [3]. The computational time complexity of the UC problem increases exponentially as the size of a network is increased [4]. The biggest expense associated with the unit commitment problem is fuel usage [5]. The reference [6] highlights the significance of accurately representing these costs by noting that a utility would gain annually millions of euros from a 0.5% fuel savings in electricity generation. To maximize profitability, research is concentrated on refining the modeling details.

In previous decades, the thermal foundation of power systems was often provided by coal plants. Fast-ramping gas turbines were employed to meet demand peaks whereas combined cycles gas turbines were reserved for times of high demand [7]. Since this organization was stable throughout time, effective asset management did not necessitate significant modeling advancements. In power system generation scheduling, two duties are taken into account. One of these is the unit commitment or UC, which establishes the unit's start-up and shutdown schedules to reduce system fuel consumption. The other is economic dispatch, which allows system load demands to committed generating units to reduce the cost of power generation [8]. The economic operation is noteworthy since a small decrease in fuel cost as a percentage results in significant system operation cost savings [9]. The unit commitment or UC dilemma typically encompasses both of these decisions because they are related. Finding the overall least expensive way to run the power system over the scheduling horizon is the goal [10]. Many studies for power system generation scheduling have successfully applied using various mathematical algorithms given in [11] that include artificial intelligence techniques e.g., Expert Systems, Fuzzy Logic systems, and Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). The AI techniques have combined practical operational strategies with mathematical techniques to

progress the system models significantly. The mechanism of ANN mimics the learning process of the human brain [12]. It has been proposed in several studies looking at the unit commitment problem that the unit's generating capability changes in steps from zero to the rated capacity and vice versa [13], and startup and shutdown costs proposed in [14], to avoid brittle failure of before online of the unit. Further, most of the authors in the literature consider unit step function to satisfy physical constraints during online units such as ramp up and ramp down [15]. All activities are started as soon as the unit reaches its rated capacity when employing a step function to reflect changes in generating capability, which indicates an unrealistic treatment of energy, especially when the unit start-up is a lengthy process [16].

Similar to how it takes time for the turbine to cool down when a unit is shutting down, so does it. Contrary to the scenario where the changes in unit-producing capacity are treated as a step function, the remaining energy is to be utilized to meet the load demand before the unit-generating capability declines to its lower limit [17]. Ramping up was once thought of as a dynamic dispatch in the economic dispatch. A dynamic procedure was carried out together with the economic dispatch to satisfy the ramping limits [18]. Dynamic Programming (DP) is considered to handle these ramping constraints in the economic dispatch sub-problem of the UC problem. DP-based algorithms are time-consuming, therefore, this study avoids DP implementation for the solution of generation scheduling [19]. In [20], a feasible and near-optimal solution to the UC problem is obtained by relaxing the ramping constraints and using step functions—in this function online generator can inject 100% of its capacity—to express the generating capabilities. After that, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) is implemented to generate possible scheduling, and a heuristic method is applied to solve the UC. In [21], dynamic dispatch is used to solve the UC problem. In recent years, researchers have shown interest and have looked for more effective ways to approach the UC problem. However, the non-convex UC problem has issues with convergence when using classical approaches [22]. These are gradient-based and experience a significant bottleneck when they hit local minima [23]. In general, the UC problem is formulated as a nonconvex Mixed Integer Nonlinear Problem (MINLP), and the scale of this problem creates challenges to solving large UC problems [24, 25]. The dramatic increase in the efficiency of MINLP solvers has encouraged the thorough exploitation of their capabilities [26].

Therefore, in this paper, a new formulation based on Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP) is applied to solve the unit commitment of conventional thermal generators. In the proposed formulation, the UC decision variables and generation scheduling variables are simultaneously obtained and applied to solve UC and the economic dispatch problem. During optimization, step length binary decision variable is obtained by using crossover and mutation operators of binary GA, whereas, continuous decision variables are searched using crossover and mutation operators of real coded GA. Moreover, in the proposed algorithm, infeasible solutions are discarded by

using an efficient feasibility rule constraint handling technique.

The rest of this article is divided into the following sections:

The unit commitment Problem formulation is provided in Section II. In section III, specifics of the suggested GA-based MINLP methodology are provided. Section IV presents proposed study cases and simulation results, while Section V conducts discussions. Section VI summarizes the conclusion.

II. PROBLEM FORMULATION

The generation scheduling challenge seeks to reduce the overall cost of system operation while adhering to the system operating limits. This cost comprises the fuel cost for producing electricity as well as the start-up and shutdown costs. The total operating cost of the UC problem can be given as:

$$C(P_g) = \sum_{t=1}^{N_t} \sum_{i=1}^N [I_i(t) \times F_i(P_i(t)) + I_i(t)(1 - I_i(t - 1))S_i(X_i^{\text{off}}(t - 1))] \quad (1)$$

Whereas, the Fuel cost of generator 'i' at a time 't' can be computed as:

$$F_i(P_i(t)) = a_i + b_i * P_i + c_i * P_i^2 \quad (2)$$

Additionally, a significant amount of energy must be used to bring the thermal unit online because the temperature and pressure of the unit must be moved slowly. As a result of the commitment and de-commitment status, this energy enters the unit commitment problem as a start-up cost $S_i(X_i^{\text{off}}(t - 1))$ but does not result in any MW integration in the system unit. Suppose, the status of unit 'i' at $I_i(t - 1)$ is OFF and it becomes ON in the next hour at $I_i(t)$, then startup cost $S_i(X_i^{\text{off}}(t - 1))$ second part of eq. (1) is applied and it depends upon the number of hours that unit i has been recommitted. If the unit was just recently shut off and is still somewhat close to operating temperature, the start-up cost can range from a maximum "cold-start" value to a much smaller value. There are two methods for handling a thermal unit while it is idle. The first enables the boiler of the appliance to cool off before heating back up to operating temperature in time for a predetermined switch-on.

If the unit is in a de-committed state for more than or equal to cold start hours (T_i, cold) after minimum off time, cold start-up $S_i(X_i^{\text{off,cold}}(t - 1))$ cost is associated with its commitment event. However, if the units are in a de-committed state after minimum off time but for less duration than cold start hours, then the hot start-up cost $S_i(X_i^{\text{off,hot}}(t - 1))$ is associated with commitment events.

Therefore, the startup cost applicable for g^{th} thermal unit during t^{th} hour given by:

$$S_i(X_i^{\text{off}}(t - 1)) = \begin{cases} S_i(X_i^{\text{off,hot}}(t - 1)) & \text{if } T_i^{\text{off}} \leq X_i^{\text{off}}(t) \leq T_i^{\text{off}} + \text{Cold}_g^{\text{H}} \\ S_i(X_i^{\text{off,cold}}(t - 1)) & \text{if } X_i^{\text{off}}(t) \geq T_i^{\text{off}} + \text{Cold}_g^{\text{H}} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

The unit start-up cost is computed as:

$$S_i \left(X_i^{\text{off}}(t) \right) = \alpha_i + \beta_i [1 - e^{X_i^{\text{off}}(t)/\tau_i}] \quad (4)$$

In the literature, most researchers neglect the shut-down cost because it is often modeled as a constant cost parameter in thermal generators. Therefore, in this paper, the shut-down cost is neglected during de-commitment as shown in eq. (1).

The constraints for the unit commitment problem are:

1) System Power Balance:

This balance equation ensures that the generation of electricity equals the load demand for each represented period. If more precise management is necessary, an energy storage term can be introduced. To indicate instances of production surpluses, it is also possible to include a spilling term in the equation. It has continuous variables in a linear equation.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_i(t) I_i(t) = D(t) * I_i(t), \quad (5)$$

2) System Spinning Reserve Requirements:

This disparity ensures a technical requirement of power systems, namely the availability of additional generation capacity set aside for risky scenarios, such as the loss of a committed thermal unit, to maintain supply security. It is a linear inequality with continuous variables as well.

$$\sum_{i=1}^N P_i^{\text{max}} I_i(t) \geq D(t) + R(t) \quad (6)$$

3) Unit Generation Limits:

This difference is used to ensure that each thermal unit's energy production adheres to the minimum and maximum power output allowed by their technological capabilities. Integer variables are used in this linear inequality.

$$P_i^{\text{min}} \leq P_i(t) \leq C_i(t) \quad (7)$$

4) Minimum-Up and Minimum-Down Constraints (Most Complicated Constraints):

To achieve technical constraints that lower the probability of failure, this inequality is used to ensure that the unit is online for a minimum duration of time since it is started up or that it is offline for a minimum period since it is shut down. It uses integer variables and is linear. Once the unit is committed then it should not be de-committed immediately and if the unit is de-committed it should not be recommitted after a minimum-down. In the proposed method min down and min up constraints can be computed as:

$$[X_i^{\text{on}}(t-1) - T_i^{\text{off}}] * [I_i(t-1) - I_i(t)] \geq 0 \quad (8)$$

$$[X_i^{\text{off}}(t-1) - T_i^{\text{off}}] * [I_i(t) - I_i(t-1)] \geq 0 \quad (9)$$

5) Ramp-Up and Ramp-Down Rate Constraints can be Computed as:

$$C_i(t) - C_i(t-1) \leq UR_i \text{ as unit } i \text{ starts up} \quad (10)$$

$$C_i(t-1) - C_i(t) \leq DR_i \text{ as unit } i \text{ shuts down} \quad (11)$$

6) Ramp-Rate Limits for Unit Generation Changes:

A thermal unit's power generation during the prior and current time steps cannot differ by more than the ramping rates thanks to this inequality. It employs continuous variables and is a linear inequality.

$$P_i(t) - P_i(t-1) \leq UR_i \text{ scheduling power is increased} \quad (12)$$

$$P_i(t-1) - P_i(t) \leq DR_i \text{ scheduling power is decreases} \quad (13)$$

Constraints in eq. (10-13) are dynamic constraints, it is necessary to formulate an algorithm that considers dynamic constraints appropriately. In the proposed formulation these constraints are checked and repaired before the computation of objective functions.

III. PROPOSED METHOD

The UC problem is a Mixed Integer Non-Linear Problem (MINLP), and the optimal solution of MINLP is hard to find using classical optimization techniques. In the last few decades, Evolutionary Algorithms (EAs), were efficiently solving the hard MINLP problems. Therefore, in this paper, a Genetic Algorithm (GA) based on MINLP methodology is applied to solve the proposed UC problem. For the application of GAs, a simple binary alphabet was chosen to encode a solution. If N represents the number of units and T the scheduling period in hours, then with the assumption that at every hour a certain unit can be either ON or OFF, an H-bit string is needed to describe the operation schedule of a single unit. In such a string, a '1' at a certain location indicates that the unit is ON at this particular hour while a '0' indicates that the unit is OFF. By concatenating the strings of the N units an N-H bit string is formed.

In the proposed formulation, the UC problem is solved by two separate measures. In the first step, UC decision variables are obtained using binary coding, in this step also, all the constraints of UC variables i.e., minimum up and down, spinning reserve are checked and repaired.

However, in the second step, decision variables of UC problems are passed to compute feasible solutions to the economic dispatch problem. Before, the evaluation of the objective function it is desirable to repair the constraints of the economic dispatch these are ramp-up and ramp-down. After satisfying all the constraints given in eq. (5-13), total operating cost along with start-up cost is computed and obtained an economical unit commitment schedule, which satisfies the system operating constraints. Between two adjacent hours, the unit state can have one of four distinct trajectories: remaining de-committed ($0 \Rightarrow 0$), starting up ($0 \Rightarrow 1$), shutting down ($1 \Rightarrow 0$), or remaining committed ($1 \Rightarrow 1$). The following three situations may need more changes due to ramping. Ramping up a unit in the 'ith' hour of a unit commitment may have an impact on the unit combinations in the next hours. The economic dispatch is the sub-problem of UC; therefore, it is evaluated after the computation of UC decision variables. The flow diagram of the proposed methodology is shown in figure I.

Figure 1: Flow Chart of Proposed MINLP-GA

Table 1: Generator Data of RTS System

Common Data						Case 1					Case 2					Case 3				
Gen. #	p^{min}	p^{max}	A	B	C	SU	RU	RD	MUT	MDT	SU	RU	RD	MUT	MDT	SU	RU	RD	MUT	MDT
1	100	800	5	4	0.001	0	100	100	1	1	415	50	50	5	5	415	15	15	5	5
2	100	800	5	6	0.002	0			1	1	625			5	5	625			5	5
3	80	400	20	8	0.0025	0			1	1	676			1	3	676			1	3
4	80	400	20	10	0.0025	0			1	1	836			5	5	836			5	5
5	60	300	30	10	0.002	0			1	1	637.2			4	1	637.2			4	1
6	60	300	30	12	0.002	0			1	1	757.2			1	3	757.2			1	3
7	50	200	40	14	0.0015	0			1	1	743.75			2	5	743.75			2	5
8	50	200	40	16	0.0015	0			1	1	843.75			3	4	843.75			3	4
9	25	100	55	15	0.0012	0			1	1	430.75			5	5	430.75			5	5
10	25	100	55	17	0.0012	0			1	1	480.75			5	4	480.75			5	4
11	25	100	55	17	0.0012	0	1	1	480.75	1	1	480.75	1	1						

SU: Startup Cost; RU: Ramp-Up (in %); RD: Ramp-Down (in %); MUT: Min-Up Time (hrs.); MDT: Min-Down Time (hrs.)

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

To examine the reliability and efficiency of the proposed method, the IEEE RTS [27] test system (11 thermal generators) is adopted to find optimal unit commitment. The data of all the generators and proposed study cases are shown in table I. The program is run on the Corei7 intel with MATLAB version R2021a. The number of populations is selected as 40 and the maximum function evaluation is taken as 10000. Furthermore, to validate the efficiency and superiority of the proposed method **three** study cases are formulated to commit thermal generators.

Case 1: Optimal UC, relaxing start-up cost, ramping constraint, min up and down constraints, and reserve for contingency is zero.

Case 2: Optimal UC at 50% ramp up and down, randomly selected min up and down time and the system spinning reserve is 400 MW.

Case 3. Optimal UC, 15% ramp up and down, randomly selected min up and down time and reserve is 800 MW.

The scheduled load demand of a week (168 hours) is given in figure II. However, the max, and min power capacity of each generator and their quadratic cost and constraint parameters are shown in table I.

Figure III shows the optimal UC schedule of Cases 1, 2, and 3 respectively. In this figure light green color indicates that the unit's generating capability is equal to its maximum capacity, however, dark blue shows that generating

capability of a unit is at its minimum capacity. Several rows indicate the number of generating units, while the columns show the time slot from 1sthr to 168thhr. In this case, UC is done by considering minimum cost only. On and off states in Case 1 follow the load curve. In this case, all 11 generators are unconstrained, which implies having a 100% ramp-up and 100% ramp-down constraint. It can be noticed that almost all 11 generating units (or at least 10) were seen committed from time 128hrs to 138hrs and the majority of units i.e. G_1 to G_6, high-efficiency generators, were operating at their maximum power capacity in that time frame. Its ramp-up, ramp limits are set to be 50%. Moreover, minimum up time (once the generator is online, at least it must run min up time) and minimum down time (once a unit is offline, it must be de-committed with at least min downtime) of all generating units are added randomly as shown in table I. Unlike the first case, the startup costs of each generator are introduced in the second case.

Figure II: Generators and Demand of Each Hour in IEEE RTS Bus System

Figure III is the UC schedule of Case 3, which placates minimum up and down time, ramp up, and ramp down constraints in all the time slots. On the other hand, spinning reserve constraints are violated in some of the time slots (details discussed later).

Figure III: Binary Decision Variable of Case 3 of UC Schedule, 800 MW of Spinning Reserve

It can be noticed that all 11 generating units were seen to be committed from time 128hrs to 138hrs, and a majority of the units were operating at their maximum power capacity in that time frame. Since the min-up and min-down times of unit 4 are 5hrs each, it stays de-committed during the 48th – 53rd hr and 145th – 149th hr of 6hrs and 5hrs respectively. The power rating of unit 4 gradually increased at the instances of 55th, 79th, 102nd, and 126th hr where the load increased and it also forced maximum generators to go online. As compared to units 3, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, and 11, the 9th Unit is committed first in starting hours as it shares the economic power since it does not approach its maximum power during the whole course. Unit 11 remained de-committed most of the time due to its lowest min-up and min-down time i.e., 1hr. From figure III, we can see that the proposed algorithm gives minimum cost subject to satisfying min up and down time constraints. Figure IV compares the overall cost of Lagrangian Relaxation (LR) and the proposed method, in which LR performs marginally better than the proposed algorithm in Case 1. Whereas, in Cases 2 and 3 proposed method beats the LR method.

To show the validation and performance of a proposed method, figure V gives the comparison of the cost function in all the study cases with the exact solution of the UC problem using the Lagrangian Relaxation method.

In Case 1, the solutions of the LR method are slightly better than those of the proposed method. Whereas, in Cases 2 and 3 proposed method gives a feasible solution compared to the LR method. In Case 2, the LR method violates 3 points. In Case 3, in most of the time slots, the LR method gives infeasible solutions. In Case 2, a violation is observed by the LR method in the 30th-36th hour time slot due to the added constraints while our proposed method remained steady. In Case 3, multiple violations were observed by the LR method due to the complexity of operational constraints.

For better visualization, the simulation results of only day 6 (starting from 121 to 144 hours), where the peak load has appeared, are analyzed as shown in table II, table III, table IV for Case 1, Case2, and Case3 respectively.

Figure IV: Total Cost of Case 1, Case 2, and Case 3

While the maximum load appeared on the sixth day, also the spinning reserve constraint does not satisfy, in an hour 130 to 135 in Case 3. In Case 1, relaxing start-up cost, ramping constraint, min up and down constraints, and

reserve for contingency is zero. Therefore, no violations occurred and the results of the proposed method are quite similar to the LR method since all constraints are relaxed. In Case 2, operational constraints are introduced and the system spinning reserve is 400 MW (based on the capacity of the second online unit). During the sixth day, when the load is maximum, it satisfies the reserve constraint. In Case 3, ramp-up and down constraints randomly selected min up and down time, and a reserve of 800 MW (based on the capacity of the largest online unit) are introduced. It is observed that on this day, the spinning reserve constraint does not satisfy in the hours 130 to 135 in Case 3. In table IV, a cumulative schedule power, cost, and constraint violation of the sixth day are shown. In Case 3, constraint violations occurred during hours 130 to 135 where the spinning reserve was taken 800 MW. Since the generation does not meet the load demand, its spinning reserve must be increased to avoid violations. After examining the results of the sixth day, it can be easily predicted that an

extra 200 MW is required to meet the spinning reserve during the contingency period. The simulation results of various study cases, (relaxed UC problem to highly constrained UC problem), show that the final optimal commitment of units does not violate any constraint. table II to table IV shows that the G_1 to G_5 are highly efficient generators and committed during base load conditions. The marginal cost of these generators is less as compared to G_6 to G_{11} , hence it is committed during the proposed time horizon. Generators G_6 to G_{11} are frequently committed and recommitted according to load profile and their cost curve. The GA-based MINLP methodology gives a near-global optimal solution to the UC problem, and it is easy to implement on any size of the realistic problem with less computational complexity. In the proposed methodology decision variables of the UC problem and its sub-problem economic dispatch are simultaneously optimized.

Figure V: Cost Comparison of all Generators in Each Hour for all the Study Cases

Table II: UC Values and Ratings of Case 1 (From 121 To 144 Hours)

Time (Hours)	Generators Scheduled Power										
	G_1	G_2	G_3	G_4	G_5	G_6	G_7	G_8	G_9	G_{10}	G_{11}
121	755.8	544.0	242.7	265.4	156.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
122	784.6	506.7	252.3	229.4	135.7	0	0	0	0	0	0
123	775.8	506.9	243.0	218.7	108.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
124	752.8	579.2	215.2	178.7	98.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
125	798.9	592.3	188.2	186.0	87.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
126	797.8	669.9	215.8	220.0	106.9	60	50	50	25	25	25
127	791.9	744.3	238.8	256.4	124.7	78.1	63.6	60.0	0	0	0
128	800	800	278.8	296.4	154.7	108.1	83.6	80.0	25	25	25
129	800.0	789.1	312.8	331.7	177.7	138.1	80.3	93.1	25	29.9	29.2
130	799.8	799.9	352.8	367.7	204.9	166.7	83.1	107.54	30.7	29.6	32.7
131	799.9	800.0	392.8	366.6	234.0	189.4	96.3	88.07	31.7	0	32.7

132	799.8	795.8	399.5	398.1	247.1	213.1	88.7	95.43	25	25	0
133	799.9	793.3	394.8	398.9	260.4	215.3	98.7	107.39	25.2	25.0	25
134	799.9	785.5	397.5	391.3	288.0	239.6	105.6	97.47	27.6	33.7	33.6
135	799.4	798.3	385.1	374.9	293.7	269.4	120.9	78.83	26.4	0	25.1
136	799.6	799.6	394.9	395.6	295.0	240.2	100.9	61.87	0	0	0
137	800.0	795.9	395.6	366.2	292.2	221.7	83.4	0	0	0	0
138	749.8	753.4	368.5	326.6	266.1	191.8	63.4	0	0	0	0
139	799.0	694.6	337.5	286.6	263.3	161.9	0	0	0	0	0
140	761.2	641.3	302.6	282.9	237.6	145.3	0	0	0	0	0
141	782.5	563.1	263.1	258.6	209.7	126.8	0	0	0	0	0
142	702.5	483.1	223.1	218.6	179.7	96.8	0	0	0	0	0
143	639.5	413.3	188.6	179.2	152.8	75.3	0	0	0	0	0
144	583.3	363.0	153.9	139.8	123.1	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table III: UC Values and Ratings of Case 2 (From 121 To 144 Hours)

Time (Hours)	Generators Scheduled Power										
	G ₁	G ₂	G ₃	G ₄	G ₅	G ₆	G ₇	G ₈	G ₉	G ₁₀	G ₁₁
121	789.5	580.3	239.5	191.9	165.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
122	763.8	597.8	208.0	200.5	138.4	0	0	0	0	0	0
123	767.1	604.2	169.2	184.1	127.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
124	780.8	567.7	179.1	194.2	102.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
125	759.3	632.2	169.3	171.1	120.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
126	799.1	710.9	198.4	185.1	142.0	60	50	50	25	25	0
127	789.7	788.3	218.5	189.5	136.1	78.6	55.0	50	25.9	26.2	0
128	800	800	258.5	229.5	166.1	108.6	75.0	69.9	35.9	36.2	25
129	800.0	799.6	298.5	269.3	194.9	137.3	93.6	88.2	45.6	45.6	34.3
130	800.0	800.0	336.7	298.7	222.8	167.1	107.0	97.7	55.1	47.7	42.5
131	799.5	797.0	376.7	310.2	247.0	192.6	97.6	77.9	48.8	38.0	46.5
132	796.2	797.5	399.8	344.2	263.9	207.2	105.5	65.3	43.8	28.0	36.5
133	799.9	796.5	400.0	353.4	282.1	223.9	91.8	79.9	46.6	34.7	35.2
134	800.0	800.0	399.7	391.6	299.3	251.7	109.2	78.6	40.9	0	28.9
135	798.3	799.2	397.1	362.8	296.7	271.5	117.8	58.6	38.9	0	31.0
136	800.0	786.3	372.1	386.6	299.6	256.0	97.9	60.7	29.1	0	0
137	784.1	780.7	383.5	349.4	299.9	229.5	77.9	50.0	0	0	0
138	747.2	770.8	345.2	318.1	280.9	199.5	58.0	0	0	0	0
139	800.0	719.4	312.0	278.1	259.6	173.9	0	0	0	0	0
140	784.6	682.6	287.2	238.1	229.8	148.6	0	0	0	0	0
141	740.9	635.7	298.3	210.4	199.8	118.6	0	0	0	0	0
142	660.9	555.7	258.3	170.4	169.8	88.6	0	0	0	0	0
143	599.6	529.5	225.5	146.9	147.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
144	519.6	449.5	185.5	106.9	117.2	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table IV: UC Values and Ratings of Case 3 (From 121 To 144 Hours)

Time (Hours)	Generators Scheduled Power										
	G ₁	G ₂	G ₃	G ₄	G ₅	G ₆	G ₇	G ₈	G ₉	G ₁₀	G ₁₁
121	796.5	622.5	252.2	116.1	122.9	0	54.8	0	0	0	0
122	778.4	652.6	240.8	81.3	102.2	0	53.5	0	0	0	0
123	794.0	626.8	204.6	110.4	116.6	0	0	0	0	0	0
124	797.8	607.1	185.0	132.0	102.7	0	0	0	0	0	0
125	781.6	643.0	216.0	112.7	99.2	0	0	0	0	0	0
126	799.9	722.9	255.9	152.4	129.2	60	0	50	25	25	25
127	799.9	788.9	284.0	192.4	121.1	63.8	0	54.6	27.4	25.6	0
128	800	800	324.0	232.4	151.1	93.8	50	74.6	37.4	35.6	25
129	800.0	799.7	364.0	272.0	180.6	123.8	63.2	94.6	40.1	36.3	32.7
130	799.2	799.9	398.2	310.5	206.5	153.8	80.1	109.7	48.6	36.0	35.9
131	799.1	792.2	387.7	341.0	214.4	181.7	73.3	126.1	45.9	40.5	31.2
132	795.2	789.5	385.6	378.9	218.7	204.0	76.7	131.4	36.6	37.8	36.7
133	791.9	797.4	379.0	395.5	218.9	210.9	78.8	142.7	39.9	43.7	45.8
134	797.6	781.7	397.1	399.1	230.6	240.8	95.1	135.1	30.1	40.4	53.7
135	788.2	791.6	397.1	399.3	227.1	241.4	84.0	117.5	39.1	31.1	57.3
136	760.5	787.7	366.6	391.0	250.8	214.9	70.9	129.0	29.7	29.6	62.8
137	742.3	724.6	331.0	356.9	261.6	217.8	67.4	130.8	39.6	37.2	52.9
138	696.9	681.7	291.0	331.5	250.9	203.1	54.1	110.8	29.6	27.2	42.9
139	775.9	624.9	306.8	291.5	221.8	173.1	0	90.8	25.3	0	33.0

140	758.8	659.7	284.4	255.6	198.2	143.1	0	71.2	0	0	0
141	799.9	590.7	251.3	215.6	176.2	118.9	0	51.2	0	0	0
142	719.9	510.7	211.3	175.6	146.2	88.9	0	0	0	0	0
143	717.2	460.2	190.8	135.6	144.9	0	0	0	0	0	0
144	637.2	380.2	150.8	95.6	114.9	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table V: Cumulative Schedule Power, Cost, and Constraint Violation of Sixth Day

Time (Hours)	$\sum_{i=1}^{11} P_{Gi}$			$\sum_{i=1}^{11} C_i$			CV		
	Case1	Case2	Case3	Case1	Case2	Case3	Case1	Case2	Case3
121	1964.834	1964.818	1964.9	14068.14	13683.23	14543.26	0	0	0
122	1908.746	1908.699	1908.69	13385.17	12899.74	13796.29	0	0	0
123	1852.534	1852.543	1852.565	12843.22	12366.41	12669.09	0	0	0
124	1824.467	1824.462	1824.464	12513.27	12000.68	12229.09	0	0	0
125	1852.532	1852.532	1852.533	12596.63	12382.34	12572.67	0	0	0
126	2245.524	2245.525	2245.514	17818.38	21215.47	20714.14	0	0	0
127	2357.796	2357.799	2357.795	18429.07	18484.85	18532.18	0	0	0
128	2676.635	2587.167	2646.557	22496.8	21914.52	22511.09	0	0	0
129	2806.968	2797.167	2806.918	24069.99	24059.39	24046.86	0	0	0
130	2975.362	2969.514	2975.413	26044.57	26331.26	26274.87	0	0	73.71271*
131	3031.48	3031.484	3033.373	26361.09	26996.99	27045.29	0	0	15.75697*
132	3087.688	3087.637	3089.345	26990.77	27533.4	27692.04	0	0	40.55666*
133	3143.773	3143.76	3147.938	27924.67	28159.82	28535.15	0	0	113.3411*
134	3199.903	3199.934	3201.573	28680.39	28603.1	29121.66	0	0	159.2334*
135	3171.836	3171.94	3173.554	28047.87	28106.86	28740.9	0	0	69.34376*
136	3087.624	3087.89	3090.46	26545.29	26967.57	27778.07	0	0	0
137	2954.948	2955.884	2973.209	24614.5	24953.08	26335.44	0	0	0
138	2719.685	2720.519	2720.253	22259.25	22063.47	23414.48	0	0	0
139	2542.883	2542.884	2542.882	19899.51	19878.15	21062.58	0	0	0
140	2370.964	2370.978	2370.953	18358.87	18074.33	18854.21	0	0	0
141	2203.847	2203.847	2203.848	16635	16435.92	16869.26	0	0	0
142	1903.847	1903.847	1833.233	14035.67	13822.51	13039	0	0	0
143	1648.589	1648.593	1648.622	11856.92	11298.45	11407.4	0	0	0
144	1363.059	1378.593	1378.622	9193.132	9152.786	9272.438	0	0	0

* Spinning Reserve Constraint Violated

V. LIMITATIONS

Introducing a hybrid algorithm for Mixed Integer Nonlinear Programming (MINLP)-based Unit Commitment presents promising advancements over classical methods; however, several limitations must be considered. Firstly, the increased complexity and demand for computational resources due to the integration of multiple techniques could hinder practical implementation, especially for large-scale problems. Secondly, the process of tuning parameters across various problem instances for optimal performance poses a significant challenge. Additionally, ensuring the algorithm's robustness, generalization capability, and adaptability to different problem characteristics are vital factors. Despite potentially improved convergence properties, concerns regarding solution quality, scalability, and computational efficiency must be addressed. Moreover, the sensitivity to initial conditions and the interpretability of the algorithm's decision-making process remain significant considerations. However, the adaptive control techniques [28] used in robotic manipulator control could inspire adaptive mechanisms within the hybrid evolutionary algorithm. By incorporating adaptive strategies, the algorithm could dynamically adjust its parameters or search strategies during the optimization process. Reinforcement learning algorithms [29], such as Q-Learning or Deep Q-Networks (DQN), can learn optimal decision-making policies through trial and error. By applying similar principles to the Unit Commitment (UC)

problem, the hybrid evolutionary algorithm could dynamically learn and refine its search strategies based on feedback received during the optimization process, potentially leading to more efficient and effective solutions.

VI. CONCLUSION

The scheduling of thermal generating units is two linked optimization problems. One is a Unit Commitment (UC) problem and the other is an economic dispatch sub-problem. The optimal solution to this problem is a vital step in the daily operational planning of the power system. In this paper, a new formulation is proposed, in which an approximate optimal solution to the UC problem is obtained by searching the simultaneous UC and economic dispatch decision variables. The UC variables (binary 0 for OFF and 1 for ON) are searched by using binary coded GA, whereas, decision variables of economic dispatch problem (continuous values of power generation) are searched by real coded GA. Moreover, various operational constraints i.e., spinning reserve, minimum and maximum capacity of generation, start-up cost, ramp-up and ramp-down, and minimum-up and down time constraints are implemented for the week ahead (168 hours) planning. Several case studies are conducted to examine the impacts of operational constraints on the cost of thermal generators. Simulation results show that the proposed method can find an approximate near global optimal solution of UC. Furthermore, the results of the proposed algorithm are analyzed and compared with the LR method. In Case 3,

where all the constraints along with 800 MW of the spinning reserve are considered, the LR method gives a larger number of infeasible solutions than the proposed algorithm. The next wave in the field of power systems is highly concentrated on moving away from conventional deterministic techniques to stochastic optimization for the UC problem. That is due to the high penetration of renewable energy, increased deregulation of the electrical businesses, and increasing demands on system reliability. Therefore, in the future, the proposed methodology for the solution of the UC problem can be extended by considering the uncertain wind and solar integration.

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Authors Contributions

All the authors; equally contributed to this study.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest and confirm that this work is original and not plagiarized from any other source, i.e., electronic or print media.

Data Availability Statement

The testing data is available in this paper.

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